

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15584716

Larvicidal Impact Of *Syzygium Aromaticum* In The Control Of *Aedes aegypti*, A Vector Of Numerous Pathogens

Ernest Olaolu Dawodu

Department of Agricultural Science and Technology,
Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology,
Ikere-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The potency of *Syzygium aromaticum* essential oils to control larvae of *Aedes aegypti* was examined at various levels of concentration 10 ppm – 70 ppm. Data was collected at intervals from the initial time of treatment application of 1hr: 20 min., hours after time of application (HAT), mortality was determined. All treatment means showed evidence of control of the mosquito. Data collected was subjected to ANOVA, and lethal time per concentration was further determined. The presence of phytochemicals, concentration of treatment and time of exposure of the insect to the botanicals is suspected to have contributed to the control achieved.

Keywords: *Aedes aegypti*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, Spinosad, Essential oil, Control

INTRODUCTION

Mosquitoes are vectors of life threatening diseases such as dengue fever, filariasis, zika fever, Japanese encephalitis and yellow fever (Reuda, 2008; Balenghien *et al.*, 2010; WHO, 2022). In Nigeria, loss of lives due to the scourging effect of mosquito to man and animals has been reported. The world population is at a risk with the yearly increase of about 400 million infectious rate of dengue (WHO, 2018). This have negative effect on human health and survival which cost the population reduced economic activity and creativity (WHO, 2004). As a result of this, a far reaching total economic loss on the African continent is recorded (WHO, 2004; Hotez *et al.*, 2009). Mosquitoes transmits pathogens into the system of man while trying to get the required blood meal for egg development (Balenghien *et al.*, 2010). The rate of blood meal digestion is determined by the prevailing environmental temperature, the higher the temperature the faster blood meal digestion and thus shorter gonotrophic cycle duration and higher biting frequency by mosquitoes (Tjaden *et al.*, 2013; Carrington *et al.*, 2013; Xian-Yi Jian *et al.*, 2023). Incidentally, the geographical location of Nigeria, implicates her with adequate vegetative cover, temperature fluctuation which enhances rate of development of plasmodium parasites and consequently the capacity of malaria vectors increases. This calls for attention to reduce the rate of multiplication of this human pest so as to achieve a correlative reduction in diseases incidence. Synthetic insecticides have been the prevalent means of control. This comes with its attendant problems of human poisoning, environmental pollution with effect on the flora and fauna, high cost of purchase and inadequate technical knowhow (Allso *et al.*, 2015; Dawodu *et al.*, 2021). There has been the campaign that the majority of mosquito control programmes should discontinue the use of synthetic insecticides due to high cost of synthetic insecticides, destabilization of the ecosystem as a result of pollution, harmful effect on human health, non-biodegradable composition of the insecticides and the increasing rate of resistant development by the target pests (WHO, 1996). Consequent upon these, there is need to find alternative method of controlling this pest. Over the years, plants with insecticidal properties have been found useful in

different pest control programmes (Babarinde *et al.*, 2017; Dawodu, 2022). *Syzygium aromaticum* (L.) Merr. & L.M. Perry is a genus of flowering plants of the family Myrtaceae. It is an evergreen shrub which has its origin in Africa and spreads to Asia. It has demonstrated antimicrobial activity against microorganisms which causes diseases associated with low immunity in man (Cock and Cheesman, 2019). Reports of the use of essential oils from clove *S. aromaticum* for the control of storage pest of maize has been documented to control insect pests (Batiha *et al.*, 2020; Babarinde *et al.*, 2022). Control of *A. aegypti* with the use of essential oils from eugenol derivatives was reported (Barbosa *et al.*, 2012). The reports of health implications on human, animals and environment by the over-dependence on poisonous synthetic insecticides in the name of controlling mosquito, *A. aegypti* are serious concerns (WHO, 2022). The vector of viral life-threatening diseases such as yellow fever, filariasis, dengue, zika virus and Japanese encephalitis have direct impact on the economy and the human population in sub-Saharan Africa. Therefore, its population should be brought below economic threshold (Chastel, 2009; Hotez *et al.*, 2009). Investigation into other ecofriendly and ecologically sound methods of controlling this pest is paramount. Earlier studies on botanicals revealed that they could be explored. Till date, adequate studies on the formulations from botanicals which are suitable for commercial purpose to replace synthetic insecticides for the control of *A. aegypti* is still indented. Therefore, this research attempts to fill that research gap.

METHODOLOGY

Site: The research was carried out in the Crop Science laboratory of the Department of Agricultural Science and Technology, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology (BOUESTI), Ikere-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Insect and culture preparation: The adult and larvae of *Aedes aegypti* was collected from the livestock unit of the teaching and research farm of BOUESTI, Ikere-Ekiti. 10 adult poultry birds were be put in a netted battery cage along with the larvae and adult of *A. aegypti*, so as to serve as source of blood for *A. aegypti*. Newly emerged larvae and adults were used for the bioassay.

Botanicals: The botanical (*Syzygium aromaticum*) used for the bioassay was obtained from the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN) where authentication was made and respective voucher numbers was documented. Essential oil was extracted from the plant material through Hydro-distillation with the aid of Clevenger type apparatus (British Pharmacopoeia, 1980).

Botanical oil was stored in glass container under refrigerated condition till use.

Larvicidal Bioassay: Essential oil extracted from the botanical was used. The procedures of testing the larvicidal activities as provided by WHO (2005) was adopted.

Concentration of 10-70 ppm was used. 35 ppm Spinosad serve as control experiment with a replication of each experiment 5 times. 20 specimens of 3rd, 4th and 5th instar of the larvae were assayed.

Mortality of larvae was determined every 20 minutes. Percentages of dead larvae was determined. Each formulated botanical stored in glass container under refrigerated condition was used to evaluate its potency over the storage period. The procedure for larvicidal bioassay described above was repeated at 2, 4 and 6 months after the production of the botanical formulation.

Data analysis: The data collected was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using statistical analysis system (SAS) version 9.3 software and significant means was compared at 5 % significant level using Tukey's HSD Test. Probit analysis was subsequently carried out to determine the lethal time (LT₅₀ and LT₉₀).

RESULTS

Table 1: Comparative effect of *Syzygium aromaticum* and Spinosad against *Aedes aegypti*

Treatments	Concentrations (ppm)	Times of Exposure (Minutes)				
		1:20	1:40	1:60	1:80	1:100
Control	0	0.00 ^H	0.00 ^I	1.00 ^I	1.00 ^K	3.00 ^L
3 rd Instar	10	0.00 ^H	0.00 ^I	0.00 ^I	3.00 ^K	4.00 ^L
	20	0.00 ^H	1.00 ^{HI}	3.00 ^H	5.00 ^I	6.00 ^K
	30	0.00 ^H	1.00 ^{HI}	4.00 ^{GH}	5.00 ^I	6.00 ^K
	40	2.00 ^{FG}	3.00 ^{FG}	5.00 ^{FG}	6.00 ^{HI}	8.00 ^J
	50	2.00 ^{FG}	3.00 ^{FG}	6.00 ^{EF}	6.00 ^{HI}	8.00 ^J
	60	4.00 ^{DE}	6.00 ^{CD}	8.00 ^{CD}	9.00 ^{EF}	12.00 ^{EF}
	70	4.00 ^{DE}	5.00 ^{DE}	11.00 ^B	13.00 ^C	16.00 ^B
4 th Instar	10	0.00 ^H	0.00 ^I	3.00 ^H	3.00 ^J	6.00 ^K
	20	0.00 ^H	2.00 ^{GH}	3.00 ^H	6.00 ^{HI}	7.00 ^{JK}
	30	0.00 ^H	2.00 ^{GH}	4.00 ^{GH}	6.00 ^{HI}	8.00 ^J
	40	3.00 ^{EF}	4.00 ^{EF}	7.00 ^{DE}	9.00 ^{EF}	9.00 ^{HI}
	50	4.00 ^{DE}	4.00 ^{EF}	8.00 ^{CD}	9.00 ^{EF}	10.00 ^{GH}
	60	4.00 ^{DE}	7.00 ^{BC}	9.00 ^C	11.00 ^D	14.00 ^{CD}
	70	7.00 ^B	8.00 ^B	12.00 ^B	15.00 ^B	16.00 ^B
5 th Instar	10	1.00 ^{GH}	4.00 ^{EF}	6.00 ^{EF}	8.00 ^{FG}	8.00 ^J
	20	3.00 ^{EF}	4.00 ^{EF}	5.00 ^{FG}	8.00 ^{FG}	8.00 ^J
	30	4.00 ^{DE}	4.00 ^{EF}	6.00 ^{EF}	7.00 ^{GH}	9.00 ^{HI}
	40	5.00 ^{CD}	6.00 ^{CD}	8.00 ^{CD}	9.00 ^{EF}	11.00 ^{FG}
	50	6.00 ^{BC}	7.00 ^{BC}	9.00 ^C	10.00 ^{DE}	13.00 ^{DE}
	60	6.00 ^{BC}	6.00 ^{CD}	11.00 ^B	13.00 ^C	15.00 ^{BC}
	70	12.00 ^A	13.00 ^A	16.00 ^A	17.00 ^A	20.00 ^A

Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different at 5 % probability

When *A. aegypti* larvae were exposed to the treatments at 1: 20min. HAT, there was mortality in all *S. aromaticum* concentrations except in lesser concentrations 10- 30 ppm and in Spinosad. Highest mortality was recorded in *S. aromaticum* 70 ppm in the 3rd, 4th, and 5th instar while the lowest mortality was recorded in the control. At 1:40 HAT, *S. aromaticum* at 70 ppm same trend was observed. At 1:60 HAT, significantly higher mortality 16.00 was recorded despite the mortality recorded in the spinosad treatment which was insignificant 1:00. At treatment with *S. aromaticum* in 1:80- 1:100 HAT consistently superior effect (13:00-16:00 3rd instar; 15:00-16:00 4th instar; 17:00-20:00 5th mortality) to other treatments was recorded, while Spinosad caused 1:00-3:00 mortality (Table 1).

Table 2: LT₅₀ and LT₉₀ of *Aedes aegypti* to *Syzyzin armaticum* and Spinosad

Times of Exposure (minutes)	LC ₅₀ / LC ₉₀		
	3 rd Instar	4 th Instar	5 th Instar
1:20	199ppm /831ppm	125ppm /407ppm	83ppm /426ppm
1:40	138ppm /575ppm	95ppm /331ppm	100ppm /584ppm
1:60	75ppm /245ppm	63ppm /182ppm	51ppm /389ppm
1:80	79ppm /501ppm	51ppm /218ppm	36ppm /316ppm
1:100	62ppm /309ppm	47ppm/239ppm	26ppm /102ppm

The result of probit analysis followed the same trend as the analysis of variance. When *S. aromaticum* was applied at 1:20 HAT, the effect of the LT_{50/90} was lesser than the value obtained in application of *S. aromaticum* at 1:60 HAT [75ppm/ 245ppm] and the value obtained when *S. aromaticum* [62ppm/309ppm] was applied 1:100 HAT. The result indicates that application of *S. aromaticum* at 1:60 HAT performed better than that applied at 1:20 HAT. While the application of *S. aromaricum* at 1:100 HAT performed best in all 3rd, 4th and 5th instar. Invariably, time was a factor in the lethal efficacy (Table 2).

The results of this study shows that extracts from *S. aromaticum* contains toxicants which are poisonous to *A. aegypti*. The determinant factors of the efficacy of poisoning to *A. Aegypti larvae* were concentration and period of time which the larvae was subjected to treatment. Previous studies on the toxicant effect of botanical formulation have reported that time of exposure and application dose/ rate have often determined toxicity (Babarinde *et al.*, 2016; Ileke *et al.*, 2021; Dawodu, 2022). As time of exposure increases, and there was increase in concentration, mortality also increased. This is corroborated by earlier report about the toxicity of *Afromomum melegueta* leaf and seed extracts against *Anopheles* species which increased with an increase in concentration (Ileke *et al.*, 2017). The efficacy of toxicity in *S. aromaticum* is directly related to experimental design whereby the insects were treated in a closed chamber. Similarly, the toxicity of *S. aromaticum* to the insects may have been directly related to the bioactivity of the compounds present in it. Earlier reports have confirmed the bioactivity of phytochemicals present in *S. aromaticum* which include tanins, terpenoids, alkaloids, triterpenes. flavonoids, glycosides, coumarins (Talati *et al.*, 2012; Dawodu, 2025).

Compounds Precocene I and Precocene II from extracted essential oils of *A. conyzoides* have been implicated in the larvicidal effect exhibited against *A. albopictus* (Liu and Liu, 2014; Bora *et al.*, 2025). In a similar reports of the toxicant effect of Pectolinarigenin compounds present in *Clerodendrum phlomidis* against *Anophelis stephensi* and *Earias vittella*, high mortality was recorded on the mosquito larvae. Similarly, *Aedes Aegypti* larvae were vulnerable to the bioactive compounds present in *S. aromaticum* extract.

The results of the probit analysis indicated that the application of essential oils of *S. aromaticum* for 1:20 HAT at 3rd, 4th and 5th instar irrespective of the concentration was lethal to *Ae. Aegypti* larvae when compared with the control. However, 1:100 HAT application of *S. aromaticum* was superior to other treatments. The ANOVA results also affirmed the superior toxicity of 1:100 HAT with *S. aromaticum* over other treatments. This is in agreement with the reports of Bora *et al.*, 2025, as superior activity of organophosphate and pyrethroids compared with the essential oils of *A. conyzoides* against dengue, zika and chikungunya.

This result has established the fact that *S. aromaticum* has the potentials of controlling *A. aegypti* and could be included in an Integrated Pest Management of the dengue vector.

CONCLUSION

The effect of extracts from *S. atomaticum* was determined on the 3rd, 4th and 5th instar *Aedes aegypti*, with Spinosad as source of comparison. Mortality of larvae was recorded at 1:20, 1:40, 1:60, 1: 80 and 1:100 HAT. Data was subjected to analysis of variance. Probit analysis was carried out at estimated lethal time of (LT₅₀ and LT₉₀). At 1:100 HAT *S. atomaticum* was consistently superior (70ppm) to other treatments, while the control (Spinosad) caused 1.00-3.00 mortality compared 16:00 in *S aromaticum* in 3rd, 4th, and 5th instar. The toxicity effect exhibited by *S. aromaticum* showed that it could be a veritable source for the control of *A. aegypti*.

Authors Contribution Statement

Conceptualization: Conceptualization of the study was carried out by Ernest Olaolu Dawodu.

Data Collection: Conducted by the author.

Laboratory and Data Analysis: Performed by the author

Resources: Provided by the author

Writing- Original draft: Prepared by the author

Draft review and Editing: The final draft was carefully reviewed by the author.

Fund Statement

The success of the research work is credited to funding made available by Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) under the Institutional-Based Research (IBR) scheme. This was made possible through Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti and the Center for Research and Development (CERAD) BOUESTI, who midwived the process.

Conflict of Interest: None

Acknowledgement

The author wish to acknowledge the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) for making available funding for the research work. Appreciation also goes to the Vice-Chancellor, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology who created a conducive research environment through the Center for Research and Development (CERAD) BOUESTI.

REFERENCES

- Abdellatif F., Boudjella H., Zitouni A. and Hassani A. (2014) Chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of the essential oil from leaves of Algerian *Melissa officinalis* L. *EXCLI Journal Experimental and Clinical Science* **13**:772-781.
- Abdollahzadeh, G., Sharifzadeh, M.S. and Damalas, C.A. (2015). Perception of the beneficial and harmful effects of pesticides among Iranian rice farmers influence the adoption of biological control. *Crop Protection*, **75**:124-131.
- Adedire, C.O. and Akinneye J.O. (2004). Biological activity of tree marigold, *Tithonia diversifolia*, on cowpea seed bruchid, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Annals of Applied Biology*, 144(2): 185-189.
- Ajayi, O.J.T., Arokoyo, J.T., Nesan, O.O., Olaniyam, M., Ndire, M. and Kannike, O.A. (1987). Laboratory assessment of the efficacy of some local plant materials for the control of storage insect pests. *Samaru Journal of Agricultural Research* **5**: 81-85.
- Akinyemi OA, Babarinde SA, Oyerinde RM, Aderonbi AA. Bioactivity of a cetone and chloroform extracts of *Xylopiya aethiopica* (Dunal) A. Rich seed against *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Journal of Biologically Active Products from Nature*. 2016; **6**(5-6): 412-423.
- Alao, F.O. and Adebayo, T.A (2011) Comparative toxicology of botanical and synthetic insecticides against major field insect pests of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L) (Walp). *Journal of Natural Products and Plant Resources*, 1 (3): 86-95.
- Allso, P. M., Huxdorff, Johnston, P., Santillo, D. and Thompson, K. (2015). Pesticide and our health, a growing concern. *Green peace research laboratories, scheo of business, innovation center, university of Exeter, Exeter, UK*.

- Asadi-Samani M., Kooti W., Aslani E. A-and Shirzad H.A. (2016) A systematic review of Iran's medical plants with anticancer effect. *Journal of Evidence Based Complementary Alternative Medicine*. 21: 143-153
- Ayinde BA, Odigie F. Larvicidal properties of the volatile oil of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. (Compositae) against *Culex* species mosquito larvae. *Nigerian Journal of Applied Science*. 2001; 19: 23-25.
- Babarinde SA, Akintoye OP. Exploring varietal resistance and *Ocimum gratissimum* essential oil for groundnut protection against khapra beetle, *Trogoderma granarium*. *Integrated Protection of Stored Products IOBC-WPRS Bulletin*. 2024; 173: 53-58
- Babarinde SA, Ewete FK. Comparative bioactivity of three *Khaya* species (Meliaceae) against *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Journal of the Entomological Research Society*. 2008; 10(1): 27-35.
- Babarinde SA, Pitan OOR, Olatunde GO, Ajala, MO. Chemical composition of the essential oil of Nigeria grown *Hoslundia opposita* VAHL (Lamiaceae) dried leaves and its bioactivity against cowpea seed bruchid. *Chemistry and Biodiversity* 2017; 14 (6) DOI: 10.1002/cbdv.201600418
- Babarinde, G.O., Babarinde, S.A., Agboola, D.O. and Ajayeoba, S.I. (2011). Effect of harvesting methods on physiochemical and microbial qualities of honey. *Journal of Food and Science Technology*, 48(5) 628-634.
- Babarinde, S.A. and Ewete, F.K. (2008). Comparative bioactivity of three *Khaya* species (Meliaceae) on *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Journal of Entomological Research Society* 10 (1): 27-35.
- Babarinde, S.A., Adeyemi, O.A., Odewole, A.F., Yisa, S., Oke, O.O. and Adeyemo, A.O. (2016). Phytochemical composition and insecticidal properties of mechanically extracted castor seed oil against cowpea seed bruchid (*Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius) infesting Bambara groundnut. *Elixir Agriculture* 92: 39086-39092.
- Babarinde, S.A., Pitan, O.O.R., Ajala, M.O. and Olatunde, G.O. (2017). Insectifungal and insecticidal potentials of two tropical botanical essential oils against cowpea seed bruchid. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. DOI 10.1007/s11356-017-9589-x
- Balenghien, T., Carron, A., Sinagre, G. and Bicout, D.J. (2010) Mosquito density forecast from flooding: population dynamics model for *Aedes capius* (Pallas). *Bulletin Entomolgy Research* 100:247-254.
- Barbosa, J.D., Silva, V.B., Alves, P.B., Gumina, G., Santos, R.L., Sousa, D.P., and Cavalcanti, S.C. (2012). Structure-activity relationships of eugenol derivatives against *Aedes aegypti* (Diptera: Culicidae) larvae. *Pest management Science*, 68:1478-1483, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.3331>.
- Batitha, G.E.-S., Alkazmi, L.M., Wasef, L.G., Beshbishy, A.M., Nadwa, E.H., Rashwan, E.K. (2020). *Syzygium aromaticum* L. (Myrtaceae): Traditional uses, Bioactive chemical constituents, Pharmacological and Toxicological activities. *Biomolecules*, 10:202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10020202>.
- Bioka, D., Banyikwa, F.F. and Choudhuri, M.A. (1993). Analgesic effects of a crude extract of *Ageratum conyzoides* in the rat. *Acta Hort*. 332: 171-176.
- Bjorling-Povlsen, M., Andersen, I.R. and Grandjean, P. (2008). Potential developmental neurotoxicity of pesticides used in Europe. *Environmental Health*. 7:50.
- Bora, D., Agrahari, J., Phukan, A., Kakoti, B., Chhetry, S., Puzari, K., Saikia, I., Bardhan, S. and Borah, H. (2025). Synergistic action of essential oils of *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Eucalyptus globulus* and synthetic insecticides against mosquito vector, *Aedes albopictus* Skuse (Diptera: Culicidae). *The Journal of Basic and Applied Zoology*. 86(24):2025 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41936-025-00443-8>
- British Pharmacopoeia II. (1980). H.M. Stationary Office, 109 London.
- Carrington, L.B., Armijos, M.V., Lambrechts, L and Scott, T.W. (2013). Fluctuation at a low mean temperature accelerate dengue virus transmission by *Aedes aegypti*. *PLOS Neglect Tropical Diseases*. 25, 7(4):e2190. Doi:10.1371/journal.pntd.0002190.PMID:23638208; PMCID: PMC3636080.

- Cock, I.E. and Cheesman M. (2019). The potential of plants of the genus *Syzygium* (MYRTACEAE) for the prevention and treatment of arthritic and autoimmune diseases. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813820-5.00023-4>
- Dawodu, E.O. (2025). Phytochemical profile of *Piper guineense* Seeds *Rosemarinus officinalis* Leaves, *Syzygium aromaticum* Buds used in the control of selected pests of stored grains. *Innovations*, **80** (3): 1056-1067
- Dawodu, E.O. (2022). Effect of *Piper guineense* and *Dennettia tripetala*, two insecticidal plants on eggs laid by female *Callosobruchus maculatus* on infested Cowpea seeds. *Himalayan journal of Agriculture*, **3**(3):1-7 <https://www.himjournals.com/journal/hja>
- Dawodu, E.O., Olaifa, J.I., Adebayo, T.A., Babarinde, S.A., Adesina, G.O. and Olaniran, O.A. (2021). Traded synthetic insecticides for postharvest crop protection in Oyo State, southwestern Nigeria. *Lautech Crop and Environmental Reviews* 1(2):55-61
- Food and Agriculture Organization/World Health Organization (2005). Food safety risk analysis, Part II, case studies, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)/ World Health Organization (WHO).
- Hotez, P.J., Fenwick, A., Savioli, L. and Molyneux, D.H. (2009). Rescuing the bottom billion through control of neglected tropical diseases. *Lancet* 373: 1570-1575.
- Ileke KD, Adesina JM, Okunola OG. Larvicidal and pupicidal potential of *Aframomum melegueta* K. Schum extracts against mosquito, *Anopheles* species. *Journal of the Entomological Research Society*. 2017; 19(1): 121-127.
- Ileke KD, Adu BW, Olabimi IO. Bioefficacy of two indigenous Nigerian botanicals on the developmental stages of malaria vector, *Anopheles gambiae* Giles [Diptera: Culicidae]. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*. 2021; 41(2): 999-1010.
- Kulkarni, N.V., Kataria, R. and Gupta, S. (2015). Evaluation of various oils on Khapra beetle, *Trogoderma granarium* Everts (Coleoptera: Dermestidae) in terms of survival of adulthood, grain damage and population build-up. *International Journal of Agricultural Science Research* **5**(5): 11-22.
- Liu XC, Liu ZL. Evaluation of larvicidal activity of the essential oil of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. aerial parts and its major constituents against *Aedes albopictus*. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*. 2014; 2(4): 345-350.
- Mahmoudi, R., Amini, K., Hosseinirad, H., Valizadeh, S., Kabudari, A. and Aali, E. (2017). Phytochemistry and insecticidal effect of different parts of *Melissa officinalis* on *Tetranychus urticae*. *Research Journal of Pharmacognosy*. 4:4:49-58.
- Mathenge, E.M., Misiani, G.O., Oulo, D.O., Irungu, L.W., Ndegwa, P.N., Smith, T.A., Killen, G.F. and Knols, B.G. (2005). Comparative performance of the Mbita trap, CDC light trap and the human landing catch in the sampling of *Anopheles arabiensis*, *An. Funestus* and culicine species in a rice irrigation in Western Kenya. *Malar Journal* 4:7.
- Muthu C., Baskar, K., Duraipandiyan, V., Ignnacimuthu, S. and Ai-Dhabi, N.A. (2015). Bioefficacy of pectolinarigenin from *Clerodendrum phlomidis* Linn. F. against *Anopheles stephensi* and bhendi fruit borer, *Earias vittella* Fab. *Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology*. 2015; 58: 358-366.
- PAN (2012). Pesticides and health hazards; facts and figures. Translation of the German publication "Pestizide und gesundheitsgefahren": Daten und fakten". *Pestizide actions-Netzwerk*. www.pan-germany.org, Hamburg.
- Raja, S.S., Singh, A. and Rao, S.J. (1987). *Animal Morphology Physiology*. 34:35
- Rasmussen P. (2011) Lemon balm- *Melissa officinalis*, also known as lemon balm, bee balm, garden balm, Melissa, melissengeist. *Journal of Prime Health Care*. 3:165-166.
- Romi R. Laboratory evaluation of the bioinsecticide spinosad for mosquito control. *Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association*. 2006; 22 (1): 93-96
- Song-Hwa Chae, Soon-Il Kim, Seong Hum Yeon, Haribalan Perumalsamy and Young-Joon Ahn (2014). Fumigant toxicity of summer savory and Lemon Balm oil constituent and efficacy of spray formulations containing the oils to B- and Neonicotinoid- Resistant Q- Biotypes of *Bemisia tabaci* (Homoptera:Aleyrodidae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 107: (1)286-292 <https://doi.org/10.1603/EC13287>

- Tjaden, N.B., Thomas, S.M., Fischer, D. and Beierkuhnlein, C. (2013). Extrinsic incubation period of Dengue: Knowledge, backlog, and application of temperature dependence. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases* 7 (6): e2207. Doi:10. 1371/journal.pntd.0002207
- World Health Organization (1996). Report of the WHO informal consultation on the evaluation on the testing of insecticides, CTD/WHO PES/IC/96.1. Geneva: WHO; 1996. p. 69.
- World Health Organization (2004). Death by cause, sex and mortality stratum in WHO Regions, estimates for 2002. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2004 [http://www.who.int/whr/2004/annex/topic/annex2.xls].
- World Health Organization (2018) Position paper-Dengue vaccines - Weekly epidemiological record; 36, 2018, 93, 457-476
- World Health Organization (2022) Dengue and severe dengue
- Xian X.Y., Jiang Y.T., Wang, M., Jia, N., Cai, T., Xing, D., Li, C.X., Zhao, T.Y., Guo, X.X. and Wu, J.H. (2023). Effect of constant temperature and daily fluctuating temperature on the transovarial transmission and life cycle of *Aedes albopictus* infected with Zika virus. *Front Microbiology*.2023 Jan 4; 13:1075362. Doi:10.3389/fmicb.2022.1075362.PMID:36687634;PMCID:PMC9845868